

**THE PROPERTY OF LONG-TERM SELF-PROTECTION FROM
DESTRUCTIVE PROCESSES OF HYDROGELS OF EQUIVALENTLY
CROSS-LINKED POLYMERS CAPABLE OF CREATING INVERSE
NANOSUSPENSION**

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***Abstract.** In the stated priority article of the corresponding scientific discovery theoretically substantiated and experimentally confirmed a previously unknown the property about long-term self-protection from destructive processes of hydrogels of equivalently crosslinked hydrophilic polymers, capable of creating reverse nanosuspension at the expense to absorbed bound water with different degrees of mineralization in the form of interconnected nanoheterogeneous associative of the colloidal water clusters, type crystalline liquids as a dispersed phase in*

nanostructured mesh cells of crosslinked polymers as a dispersion medium, the reverse nanosuspension at the same time acquires the properties of an ultra-resistant, high-viscosity mass with a visually rough (wavy) surface. The article includes the following sections: introduction; the objects and methods of research; results and their discussion; scientific and practical significance of a suspected scientific discovery; conclusions and references of literature data. The introduction provides a brief analysis of the data available in the literature and the corresponding conclusions that determine the goals and objectives of this work. Waters with various mineralizations (0;300000-400000 ppm) were used as objects of study: waste (formation) waters of oil fields "Northern Buzachi" (China "SINOPEC" Corporation); "Uzen" "Ozenmunaigas" JSC; Zhetybay" "Mangistaumunaigas" JSC ("NC "KazMunayGas" JSC-50% and 50% China); "Karazhanbasmunai" LLP ("NC "KazMunayGas" JSC-50% and CITIC Corporation Ltd of the China -50%); "Kalamkas" "Mangistaumunaigas" JSC, as well as distilled water and water from the Caspian Sea. The following grades were studied as hydrophilic polymers: MPAA-20; MPAA-10; PAA-20; PAA-10. Viscometry was the main research method. The results of the research and the corresponding conclusions unequivocally confirm the elements of the discovery set out in the formula of scientific discovery.

Scope: oilfield nanochemistry and nanophysics for increase oil recovery from layers, as well as in medicine and cosmetics for the manufacture of ointment drugs. This discovery in 2018 successfully passed pilot tests at four injection wells of the North Buzachi oil field in the Republic of Kazakhstan. The actual economic efficiency due to additional oil production is 2.24 million US dollars.

Keywords: *self-protection of hydrogels from destructive processes, reverse nanosuspension, "crystalline liquids" as a new hybrid state, reverse nanosuspension with a wavy surface.*

I.Introduction:

Hydrogel products constitute a group of polymeric materials, the hydrophilic structure of which renders them capable of holding large amounts of water in their three-dimensional networks. Extensive employment of these products in a number of industrial and environmental areas of application is considered to be of prime importance. As expected, natural hydrogels were gradually replaced by synthetic types due to their higher water absorption capacity, long service life, and wide varieties of raw chemical resources. Literature on this subject was found to be expanding, especially in the scientific areas of research [1].

Hydrophilic gels, commonly referred to as hydrogels, are networks of polymer chains, sometimes found as colloidal gels, in which water has been commonly accepted as the dispersion medium [1, 2]. It should be noted that one cannot agree with this conclusion, since The essence of the project of the scientific discovery of the authors of this article indicates the opposite: water is a dispersed medium, and the nanostructured mesh cells of cross-linked polymers together perform the function of a dispersion medium. Researchers have defined hydrogels in different ways over the years. The most common of them is that the hydrogel is a water-swollen and cross-linked polymer network obtained by a simple reaction of one or several monomers [1, 3–5]. The ability of hydrogels to absorb water arises in the presence of active hydrophilic functional groups (COOH, -OH, -CONH₂, -NH₂, -SO₃H, etc.) in the polymer chain.

During last three decades, natural Hydrogels were gradually replaced by synthetic hydrogels which has long service life, high capacity of water absorption, and high gel strength [1, 6]. The polymer engineer can design and synthesize polymer networks with molecular-scale control over structure such as cross-linking density and with tailored properties, such as biodegradation, mechanical strength, and chemical and biological response to stimuli [1, 7]. The issues of classification of hydrogels according to various characteristics have been studied by many authors [1] {classification based on source (natural or synthetic origins) [8]; classification

according to polymeric composition (homopolymeric hydrogels [9]; copolymeric hydrogels [10]; multipolymer Interpenetrating polymeric hydrogel (IPN), in semi-IPN hydrogel, one component is a cross-linked polymer and other component is a non-cross-linked polymer [10, 11]; classification based on configuration (amorphous; semicrystalline: a complex mixture of amorphous and crystalline phases; crystalline) [1]; classification based on type of cross-linking (hydrogels can be divided into two categories based on the chemical or physical nature of the cross-link junctions) [1, 12]; classification based on physical appearance (hydrogels appearance as matrix, film, or microsphere depends on the technique of polymerization involved in the preparation process [1]; classification according to network electrical charge (nonionic; ionic; amphoteric; zwitterionic (polybetaines) containing both anionic and cationic groups in each structural repeating unit [1])).

The use of hydrogels in oil production

The practical use of soft matter, which includes mobile structured media, including hydrogels, is of wide interest all over the world today. These polymer compounds, due to their rheological, thermophysical and physicochemical properties, are classified as smart (intellectual) materials. Hydrogels have already confirmed their high potential for use in bio- and regenerative medicine, pharmaceuticals, agriculture, oil production and other industries [13]. A characteristic feature of the current stage of development of the oil industry is a significant change in the structure of reserves towards an increase in hard-to-recover oils. This is due to the entry of a large number of deposits into the late stage of development [14, 15]. Currently, the efficiency of oil recovery by industrially applied methods at the late stage of oil field development around the world remains unsatisfactory. The average ultimate oil recovery for various countries and regions is approximately 25-40%. Thus, residual or non-recoverable reserves remain, on average, 60–75% of the initial geological oil reserves [16, 17]. In oil production, polymer injection is one of the most effective and cost-effective methods for enhanced oil recovery (EOR) of reservoirs. When water is injected into an oil-bearing layer, it follows the path of

least resistance (usually high permeability layers) towards lower pressure suction producing wells. If the oil in the field has a higher viscosity than the injected water, water will seep through such oil, resulting in low sweep efficiency, or bypassing the oil. Polymer injection can lead to a significant increase in oil recovery when compared to water injection. A typical polymer injection scenario involves mixing and pumping polymer over an extended period of time until approximately $1/3$ to $1/2$ of the reservoir pore volume is filled with polymer. Once such a polymer “piston” is formed, water is pumped for a long time in order to propel this polymer piston and the oil shaft ahead of it towards productive wells. In order to achieve the desired pore volume, the polymer is pumped continuously for several years [18, 19]. Polymer gels are an important material used for profile control, waterproofing, chemical flooding and hydraulic fracturing. Finally, the research potential of polymer gels in oil and gas drilling and production is proposed. The temperature resistance, salt resistance, gel strength and environmental friendliness of polymer gels need to be further improved to meet future oil and gas drilling and production specifications [20].

Before hydrogel formation, water displacement of oil occurs in the same way as in conventional waterflooding. At this stage, both of these methods have almost the same qualitative and quantitative difference from polymer flooding. This is due to the fact that a high-viscosity gel rim begins to form in the reservoir due to a chemical reaction with gel-forming reagents only after the injection of the solution of the first of them is completed and the injection of the second begins. Later, a highly viscous hydrogel barrier begins to form in the formation, in which the thickener concentration is determined by the amount of chemical reagents present at a given point in the porous medium. However, compared to the polymer rim, the mobile hydrogel region has a more vertical leading edge that extends over a greater formation thickness, like a bulldozer, this barrier pushes oil, and a zone of high oil content forms in front of it. Thus, in some cases, the method of creating movable hydrogel barriers is more efficient and cost-effective than conventional and polymer displacement methods [21]. The disadvantage of this method is that in the pore media of the formation, a

complete uniform distribution of the crosslinker with the polymer solution is not achieved for the necessary chemical reaction to occur along the crosslinking. It is known that for the implementation of a chemical reaction between the polymer and the crosslinker with the participation of the required volume of water, devices for mixing the components are used under certain laboratory and field conditions. Indeed, it is difficult to implement such an effect in reservoir conditions. Therefore, hydrogel according to the [21] method in porous reservoir conditions can only be obtained in the contact zone of separately injected components. Therefore, one should not expect special results from this method. The source also lacks quantitative data on the viscosity of the hydrogel, depending on the concentration of the polymer, crosslinker, as well as information on the durability of the hydrogel and other data. The development of high-viscosity oil (HVN) deposits in complex fractured-porous reservoirs requires the development and implementation of complex technologies that provide for the use, together with the thermal effect on the reservoir, of ways to limit water inflow, using high-viscosity gel-forming compositions, is an urgent task of modern oilfield chemistry [22]. In a very interesting and voluminous review article (2022) by forty Russian leading scientists-authors from eight authoritative organizations, the main nuances on the very topical topic "Polymers of the Future" [23] were deeply analyzed. It would be good in this article to see some well-known Russian scientists-authors in the field of oilfield chemistry available also on the topic "Polymers of the Future". In the direction of "Polymers of the Future" there are important results for the creation of high-strength hydrogels on nanocomposite bases as articular cartilage-like biomimetic compounds. It will be interesting to note the work of the famous Chinese scientist Jun Fu [24]. In this work, to create high-strength hydrogels, the author prefers multifunctional polymeric hydrophobic colloids as crosslinkers using nonionic surfactants (NSAs) of the OP-10 type; OP-7; OP-4 and block copolymers of ethylene oxides (PEO - polyethylene oxide) and propylene oxides (PPO - polypropylene oxide) with the conditional formula $H-(PEO)_{99}-(PPO)_{65}-(PEO)_{99}-OH$ and the commercial name "Pluronic F-127" [24]. OP-10; OP-7; OP-4

are toxic compounds type alkylphenol derivatives. It is known that OP-4 is a representative of hydrophobic non-ionic surfactants, and OP-7 and OP-10 are hydrophilic non-ionic surfactants [25]. As for the block copolymers of alkylene oxides on the basis of certain non-colloidal surfactants (polyhydric alcohols, amines, phenol-formaldehyde resins, epoxy resins, etc.) [25-39], they are of particular interest as hydrophilic and hydrophobic micellar systems. The block copolymer of the H-(PEO)₉₉-(PPO)₆₅-(PEO)₉₉-OH type was not very well chosen by the author [24] as hydrophobic micelles. It would be good to study block copolymers with PPO side chains as hydrophobic micelles.

Conclusions on the literature review:

- China Research Institute of Oil Field Exploration and Development of SINOPEC Corporation is one of the world's leading companies in the field of polymer injection;

- No more relevant information was found in the Russian and English literature on the main points of the discovery formula:

- • “nanophysics of reverse nanosuspensions of cross-linked hydrophilic polymers”;

- • “in the nanostructure of network cross-linked polymers”;

- • “on long-term self-protection of hydrogels from destructive processes”;

- • “property of long-term self-protection from destructive processes of hydrogels of equivalently cross-linked polymers capable of creating reverse nanosuspension”;

- • “nanostructured mesh cells of cross-linked hydrophilic polymers”;

- • “reverse nanosuspension at the same time has the properties of an ultra-resistant, high-viscosity mass with a rough (wavy) surface”;

- • “hydrogels of equivalently cross-linked hydrophilic polymers”;

- • “viscosity of hydrogels of equivalently cross-linked hydrophilic polymers”;

- • “water clusters of the type of crystalline liquids” information only on liquid crystals;
- • "crystalline liquids" information only on liquid crystals;
- indeed, according to the above formula of the scientific discovery project, for the first time, the previously unknown property of the long-term self-protection of hydrogels from destructive processes is considered for the first time equivalently cross-linked hydrophilic polymers capable of creating a reverse nanosuspension due to absorbed bound water with various degrees of mineralization (0-400000 ppm) in the form of interconnected nanoheterogeneous associative colloidal water clusters such as crystalline liquids as a dispersed phase in nanostructured mesh cells of cross-linked polymers, as a dispersion medium, while the reverse nanosuspension acquires the properties of an ultra-resistant, high-viscosity mass with a rough (wavy) surface.

II. THE OBJECTS AND METHODS OF RESEARCH

The objects of research.

Were used as objects of study: various samples of water-soluble polymers; reservoir waters (without preliminary treatment) of the “Northern Buzachi”, “Kalamkas”, “Karazhanbasmunai”, “Uzen”, “Zhetybay” fields; water of the Caspian Sea, as well distilled water.

Information for the respective oilfields:

- **"Northern Buzachi" oilfield (China “SINOPEC” Corporation):**

Necessary information on the oilfield: since 1997 the deposit has been in operation; the annual volume of oil production is ~1.8 million tons; oil emulsion is resistant; oil viscosity at 40°C 400-600 mPa·s; formation temperature 31°C; oil density $\rho=938-940 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (in terms of density it belongs to the type of "bituminous oil" [40]); water cut 92-99%; formation water salinity is 70,000 ppm [41]; sulfur 2%; paraffins ~1.5%; resins ~17.4%; asphaltenes ~5.6-5.8%; oil pour point -33°C.

- **“Uzen” oilfield of “Ozenmunaigas” JSC:**

Necessary information on the oilfield: since 1965 the deposit has been in operation; the annual volume of oil production is ~5.5 million tons; oil emulsion resistant; oil viscosity at 40°C 30-40 mPa·s; formation temperature 57-68°C; oil density $\rho=844-874 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (in terms of density, it belongs to the type “light oil” - “heavy oil” [40]); oil water cut averages 80-90%, and in some cases even reaches 98%; formation water salinity is up to 96000 ppm; paraffins ~25%; resins ~15%; asphaltenes ~3%; oil pour point 30-32°C [42, 43].

• **“Zhetybay” oilfield of “Mangistaumunaigas” JSC (50% of the China and 50% of the “NC “KazMunayGas”):**

Necessary information on the oilfield: Since 1969, “Zhetybay” field has been in operation; the annual volume of oil production is ~2.75 million tons; oil emulsion is resistant; formation temperature not less than 70°C; oil density $\rho=830-870 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (in terms of density, it belongs to the type “light oil” - “heavy oil” [40]); water cut average 71.3%; formation water salinity is up to 161000 ppm [44]; paraffins up to 25-28%; resins ~15%; asphaltenes on average 3.4%; oil pour point 30°C [45, 46];

• **“Karazhanbasmunai” LLP oilfield (“NC “KazMunayGas” JSC-50% and CITIC Corporation Ltd of the China -50%):**

Necessary information on the field: Since 1974, the “Karazhanbasmunai” field has been in operation; the annual volume of oil production is ~2 million tons; oil emulsion resistant; reservoir temperature 26°C; $\rho\approx 939-944 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (in terms of density it belongs to the type of "bituminous oil" [40]); water cut, up to 30%; formation water salinity is ~300000-400000 ppm [47]; sulfur up to 2%; paraffins 0.7-1.4%; resins up to 24%; asphaltenes, on average, 5.7%; viscosity 160-660 mPa·s).

• **"Kalamkas" oilfield of “Mangistaumunaigas” JSC.**

Necessary information on the field: since 1979, the Kalamkas field has been in operation; GOOD = ~3.6 million tons; oil emulsion resistant; formation temperature 30-43°C; $\rho\approx 902-914 \text{ kg/m}^3$ (in terms of density, it belongs to the type of “bituminous oil” [40]); water cut, up to 89%; formation water salinity is ~121,000 ppm [47];

sulfur up to 0.3%; paraffins up to 5%; resins up to 23%; asphaltenes, on average, 5.9%; oil viscosity 238 mPa·s, at 40°C [48]). Experience with polymer flooding in the Kalamkas field for the period 1980-2022 is set out in [49].

The methods of researchs.

Viscometry was the main research method. The method was carried out on a Chinese digital rotational viscometer of the NDJ-8S brand [50]. The digital display viscometer of the NDJ-8S type is a modernization of the company (Fig. 1). The device uses advanced mechanical design technology and microcomputer control technology, correct data acquisition. The display is set to blue backlight. The liquid crystal display has a high brightness. The device has a high measurement sensitivity. The test results are reliable, easy to operate, model beautifully and easily, other functions are used to measure the absolute viscosity of a Newtonian type fluid and the apparent viscosity of a non-Newtonian type fluid. The device is widely used in practice for measuring the dynamic viscosity of many liquids (oils; paints, plastics, gels, polymer solutions, drugs, jewelry, coatings, detergents, oil emulsions, commercial oils, viscoelastic systems, etc. liquids). Main technical parameters of the NDJ-8S viscometer:

Measuring range 1 - 2,000,000 mPa;

Rotor Specifications 1-4 rotors;

Rotor speed 0.3, 0.6, 1.5, 3, 6, 12, 30, 60 rpm;

The volume of liquid for measurement is 400 ml;

Measurement accuracy $\pm 2\%$;

AC power supply 220V;

Working environment temperature 5-35°C;

Relative humidity no more than 80%;

Form size 370 x 325 x 280 mm

Fig. 1. NDC-8S brand viscometer (measurement limit of the device is up to $2 \cdot 10^6$ mPa·s).

TDS meter TDS-3 is a device for measuring the total mineralization of water (Fig. 2) [51].

Fig.2. TDS-3 - a device for measuring the total mineralization of water

Description:

TDS meter - a device that is designed to measure the total number of particles (water salinity) dissolved in water (TDS - total dissolved solids) per one million water particles - ppm (parts per million), as well as water temperature. The device has an automatic temperature compensation function during measurement.

The TDS meter is used to control the level of salts and minerals, assess electrical conductivity, and also check the efficiency of cleaning filters. In order to determine the level of mineralization of water, it is enough to pour it into a glass, take a TDS meter, remove the protective cap, lower the electrodes into the water and take a measurement.

The principle of operation is based on the direct dependence of the electrical conductivity of the solution (current strength in a constant electric field created by the electrodes of the device) on the amount of compounds dissolved in water.

To measure the salinity of wastewater from the Northern Buzachi fields; "Uzen"; "Zhetybay"; "Karazhanbasmunai" and "Kalamkas" the original samples were diluted in 10; 10; 20; 50 and 15 times respectively. Hydrogels of cross-linked hydrophilic polymers with the corresponding recipes (Table 2) in volumes of 400 ml (water with various degrees of mineralization in the range of 0-400000 ppm) capable of creating a reverse nanosuspension are prepared in electric mixers with a rotation speed of 445 revolution / minute (Fig. 3). At the first stage, direct suspensions were obtained with 2-hour stirring. Then, 1% solutions of the crosslinker (in appropriate waters) are added in the mode of 10 minutes of stirring, spontaneous dispersion of the aqueous dispersion medium of direct suspensions in nanostructured mesh cells of crosslinked hydrophilic polymers occurs, as the dispersion medium of the created reverse nanosuspensions, i.e. there is a transition of suspensions from direct to reverse types. The degree of swelling was measured by the gravimetric method, according to the formula [52]:

$$\alpha = (m - m_0) / m_0$$

where, α is the degree of swelling of the gel sample under study, g/g; m is the mass of the swollen sample, g; m_0 is the initial weight of the hydrogel sample, g.

For a qualitative and quantitative assessment of the degree of gelation and structure formation by viscosity values, we proposed a new classification [41]:

- 45-500 mPa·s weak gelling, weak self-organization;
- 501-1000 mPa·s moderate gelation; moderate self-organization;
- 1001-15000 mPa·s strong gelation, strong self-organization;
- 15,001-100,000 mPa·s powerful gelation, powerful self-organization;
- 100,001–300,000 mPa·s supergelation; super self-organization;
- >300,000 mPa·s hypergelation; hyper-self-organization.

Fig. 3. Preparation of hydrogels of cross-linked hydrophilic polymers

Information about hydrophilic polymers and crosslinkers that were used in the work are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Information about hydrophilic polymers and crosslinkers

Conventional designation of polymer	Polymer Composition	Molecular weight	Degree hydrolysis, %	Crosslinker	Optimum equivalent content of crosslinker relative to polymer, %
ΜΠΑΑ-20	Sulfonated PAA	$18 \cdot 10^6$	20	CrCl_3	3 (2.6-3.3)
ΠΑΑ-20	Polyacrylamide (PAA)	$18 \cdot 10^6$	20	CrCl_3	3 (2.6-3.3)
ΜΠΑΑ-10	Sulfonated PAA	$18 \cdot 10^6$	10	CrCl_3	3 (2.6-3.3)
ΠΑΑ-10	Polyacrylamide (PAA)	$18 \cdot 10^6$	10	CrCl_3	3 (2.6-3.3)

III. RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION

The research results are shown in Table 2. According to Table 2, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. In all research options at $C_{rl}=3\%$ by weight of polymer (or in mass ratios $P : C_b = 2000 : 60 = 33.3$; $P : C_b = 2500 : 75 = 33.3$; $P : C_b = 3000 : 90 = 33.3$; $P : C_b = 3800 : 114 = 33.3$; $P : S_b = 4200 : 126 = 33.3$; $P : S_b = 5000 : 150 = 33.3$; $P : S_b = 3000 : 90 = 33.3$), and also at $C_{rl}=2.6$; 3.3% were achieved all elements of novelty in accordance with the formula of the alleged scientific discovery (section IV).

2. At $C_{rl}=5-10$, excess amounts of crosslinker in relation to the equivalent average value $C_{rl}=3$ function as of reverse suspension destructor with a transition to direct suspensions, as well as a destructor of the hydrophilic polymer itself as a result of the viscosity of the system approaches the viscosity of water;

3. For the first time, was established a previously unknown property of long-term self-protection of hydrogels from destructive processes for equivalently cross-linked hydrophilic polymers capable of creating a reverse nanosuspension.

4. Aqueous solutions of hydrophilic polymers are direct suspensions, and when crosslinkers are added, it has been established for the first time that there is a transition from direct suspensions to reverse suspensions (nanosuspensions), i.e. is descended spontaneous nanodispersion of an aqueous dispersion medium of direct suspensions in nanostructured mesh cells of cross-linked hydrophilic polymers as dispersion medium of the created reverse nanosuspensions.

5. A new hybrid state of water of the type of crystalline liquids (as a dispersed phase in nanostructured mesh cells of cross-linked hydrophilic polymers, as a dispersion medium for created reverse nanosuspensions) makes it possible to increase the viscosity of water 2,000,000 times and more, at a polymer concentration of 3000 (+90 ppm stapler); 3800 (+114 ppm crosslinker). High polymer concentrations are also highly effective, however concentrations of 3000 and 3800 are more cost effective.

6. Equivalent crosslinking of hydrophilic polymers is achieved at a mass ratio of polymer : crosslinker $\approx 33 : 1$. For each polymer, the mass ratio polymer : crosslinker should be determined experimentally [14, 53-55].

7. For the first time, it was found that excess crosslinker residues have the properties of destructuring reverse nanosuspensions in direct suspensions, resulting in the loss of the unique properties of reverse nanosuspensions: long-term self-protection of hydrogels from destructive processes; crystalline liquids; superstability of the system; a high viscosity of hydrogel; the rough (wavy) surface of the hydrogel mass disappears; there is a strong syneresis of the hydrogel; a sharp decrease in the absorption capacity of hydrophilic polymers; if all this happens in reservoir conditions, there is no efficiency of polymer injection and, over time, an undesirable effect will be observed in production wells - polymer takeaway. Therefore, the property of long-term self-protection of hydrogels from destructive processes of equivalently cross-linked hydrophilic polymers capable of creating reverse nanosuspension is a very important priority in the field of application of polymers for enhanced oil recovery. Therefore, to prevent the above negatives, crosslinking should be carried out at equivalent ratios of polymer : crosslinker.

8. For the first time, the possibility of creating ultra-high-viscosity, stable nanoinverse emulsions with maximum contents of a dispersed water phase with various degrees of mineralization (distilled water; fresh water; formation waters of various oil fields) at the level of 99.61-99.8% has been established, the absorption capacity of the studied polymers is relatively to highly mineralized (70000- 400,000 ppm) waste waters is 263-500 g/g.

9. Aqueous solutions of hydrophilic polymers are direct suspensions, and with the addition of crosslinkers it has been established for the first time that there is a transition from direct suspensions to reverse suspensions (nanosuspensions) i.e. takes place spontaneous nanodispersion of an aqueous dispersion medium of direct suspensions in nanostructured mesh cells of cross-linked hydrophilic polymers as a dispersion medium of reverse nanosuspensions.

10. Hydrogels in the form of reverse nanosuspensions have the properties of an ultra-resistant, high-viscosity mass with a visually rough (wavy) surface (first identified by the authors of the discovery under consideration).

11. As a result of interesting joint work carried out by us with scientists and specialists of the Scientific Research Institute for Exploration and Development of Oil Fields of the “SINOPEC” Corporation (China, Beijing) in the field of polymer injection, it was found that, based on the results of rheological studies of hydrogels based on natural and artificial wastewater oil fields of the Republic of Kazakhstan, there are quite serious discrepancies.

12. Theoretically substantiated and experimentally confirmed a previously unknown property about long-term self-protection from destructive processes of hydrogels of equivalently crosslinked hydrophilic polymers, capable of creating reverse nanosuspension at the expense to absorbed bound water with different degrees of mineralization in the form of interconnected nanoheterogeneous. associative of the colloidal water clusters, type crystalline liquids as a dispersed phase in nanostructured mesh cells of crosslinked polymers as a dispersion medium, the reverse nanosuspension at the same time acquires the properties of an ultra-resistant, high-viscosity mass with visually a rough (wavy) surface.

IV. SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF A SUSPECTED SCIENTIFIC DISCOVERY

Area of Scientific Importance (ASI). ASI is determined on the basis of individual points of scientific novelty of the proposed discovery:

1. For the first time, a previously unknown property of the long-term self-protection of hydrogels from destructive processes (biodegradation; chemical destruction; biochemical destruction; physical destruction) of equivalently cross-linked hydrophilic polymers capable of creating a reverse nanosuspension. **ASI:** destruction of hydrogels; applied nanocolloidal chemistry; microbiology; nanophysics; engineering chemistry; engineering physics; application of tertiary methods for extracting residual oils from oil-bearing formations at the late stages of field development.

2. Aqueous solutions of hydrophilic polymers are direct suspensions, and when crosslinkers are added, it has been established for the first time that there is a transition from direct suspensions to reverse suspensions (nanosuspensions), i.e. is descended spontaneous nanodispersion of an aqueous dispersion medium of direct suspensions in nanostructured mesh cells of cross-linked hydrophilic polymers as dispersion medium of the created reverse nanosuspensions. **ASI:** Applied Nanocolloidal Chemistry; engineering chemistry.

3. A new hybrid state of water of the type of the crystalline liquids [56] (as a dispersed phase in the nanostructured mesh cells of cross-linked hydrophilic polymers, as a dispersion medium for created reverse nanosuspensions) makes it possible to increase the viscosity of water by 2,000,000 times or more. **ASI:** nanomolecular physics; applied nanocolloidal chemistry; engineering chemistry; engineering physics; application of tertiary methods for extracting residual oils from oil-bearing formations at the late stages of field development.

4. For the first time, it was found that excess crosslinker residues have the properties of a destructor of reverse nanosuspensions in direct suspensions, resulting in the loss of a complex of unique properties of reverse nanosuspensions set forth in the discovery formula. **ASI:** nanomolecular physics; applied nanocolloidal chemistry; engineering chemistry; application of tertiary methods for extracting residual oils from oil-bearing formations at the late stages of field development.

5. For the first time, identified the possibility of creating long-term ultra-high-viscosity, stable nano-inverse emulsions with maximum contents of the dispersed water phase with different degrees of mineralization (distilled water; fresh water; formation waters of the various oil-fields) at the level of 99.61-99.75% has been established, and the absorption capacity of the studied polymers is 263-500 g/g. **ASI:** physical chemistry; applied nanocolloidal chemistry; engineering chemistry; application of tertiary methods for extracting residual oils from oil-bearing formations at the late stages of field development.

6. Aqueous solutions of hydrophilic polymers are direct suspensions, and with the addition of crosslinkers it has been established for the first time that there is a transition from direct suspensions to reverse suspensions (nanosuspensions). **ASI:** Applied Nanocolloidal Chemistry; engineering chemistry;

7. Hydrogels in the form of reverse nanosuspensions have the properties of an ultra-resistant, high-viscosity mass with a visually rough (wavy) surface, which was first discovered. **ASI:** Applied Nanocolloidal Chemistry; nanophysics; nanomolecular physics; engineering chemistry; engineering physics;

8. According to the results of rheological studies of hydrogels based on natural and artificial (model) formation waters of oil fields of the Republic of Kazakhstan, there are quite serious discrepancies. **ASI:** engineering chemistry; application of tertiary methods for extracting residual oils from oil-bearing formations at the late stages of field development.

Table 2. Values of dynamic viscosity) and of polymer (P)+crosslinker (Crl) compositions depending on P : Crl and the duration of the experiment under conditions of various polymers, waters and temperature

P : Crl, ppm	Crl, %	Dynamic viscosity (mPa·s) and desorbed water (%) of P+Crl compositions depending on, P : Crl and the duration of the experiment under conditions of various polymers and formation waters										
		2 day	7 day	15 day	1 month	3 month	0.5 y	1 year	2 year	4 y or≥	ST, st, μ	
MPAA-20 : Crl (35°C)												
Produced water of the "Northern Buzachi" field (mineralization 70000 ppm)												
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
3000	300	10	3719	726	57	6	-	-	-	-	-	destruction
3000	150	5	4294	1509	216	22	-	-	-	-	-	destruction
3000	100	3.3	54362	41761	95 782	490648	903460	~2·10 ⁶	~2·10 ⁶	1493552	1156053	reverse hst hvis
3000	90	3	78469	128286	144780	1753805	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	~2·10⁶	~2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis
3000	80	2.7	66170	103944	127247	704189	1425671	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	~2·10 ⁶	~2·10 ⁶	reverse hst hvis
3000	45	1.5	16453	33752	29483	23977	21640	-	-	-	-	reverse ²
3000	0	0	64	69	67	72	49	-	-	-	-	direct
PAA-20 : Crl (35°C) Produced water of the "Northern Buzachi" field (mineralization 70000 ppm) (35°C)												
3800	380	10	2951	894	149	8	-	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	190	5	5961	2105	419	250	9	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	150	3.9	42509	110546	291816	241352	285457	321786	306353	107660	83104	reverse ¹
3800	125	3.3	69371	259634	431695	915738	1174830	1684299	1928526	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	114	3	77 592	331637	865094	1693707	1309844	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	100	2.6	72167	290408	761353	1363719	1446833	1928635	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	57	1.5	19714	35170	31526	36137	33692	34058	-	-	-	reverse ²
3800	0	0	204	86	81	82	61	40	-	-	-	direct
MPAA-20 : Crl (35°C) Produced water of the "Northern Buzachi" field (mineralization 70000 ppm)												
3800	380	10	5478	1178	280	17	4	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	190	5	9609	2950	993	504	27	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	150	3.9	81547	251055	914248	836027	698490	820265	577682	123065	105727	reverse ¹
3800	125	3.3	83285	649175	1309933	1503912	>2·10 ⁶	reverse hst hvis				
3800	114	3	1135925	729603	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis						
3800	100	2.6	105037	717519	1625442	>2·10 ⁶	~2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	57	1.5	25242	53942	47099	61903	55194	53829	-	-	-	reverse ²

3800	0	0	279	90	94	93	67	46	-	-	-	direct
PAA-20 : CrI (43°C) Produced water of the “Kalamkas” field (mineralization 121000 ppm)												
3800	380	10	2478	803	152	5	-	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	190	5	4580	1474	293	46	4	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	150	3.9	34681	71947	195834	211529	207273	215568	212391	79910	52942	reverse ¹
3800	125	3.3	41795	149026	307861	726904	990472	1157523	1583296	1275043	1594128	reverse hst hvis
3800	114	3	45394	160915	541833	1058566	1269320	1791353	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	100	2.6	43530	154369	472918	983317	1153927	1521045	1842784	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	57	1.5	16425	29926	28051	31839	31454	32032	-	-	-	reverse ²
3800	0	0	190	81	75	76	58	40	-	-	-	direct
PAA-20 : CrI (43°C) Produced water of the “Kalamkas” field (mineralization 121000 ppm)												
3800	380	10	3754	963	179	11	-	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	190	5	7089	2360	614	311	38	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	150	3.9	57492	186513	397486	543616	588391	402684	391360	106047	93528	reverse ¹
3800	125	3.3	83671	423540	791452	1201739	1498723	1813386	~2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	114	3	869049	431578	975817	1640251	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	100	2.6	85730	427905	854036	1459625	1763417	~2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	57	1.5	22909	49178	44740	45072	43985	43483	-	-	-	reverse ²
3800	0	0	250	88	89	90	63	45	-	-	-	direct
PAA-20 : CrI (26°C) Produced water of the “Karazhanbasunai” field (mineralization 300000-400000 ppm)												
3800	380	10	4736	891	190	12	-	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	190	5	6038	2870	769	274	13	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	150	3.9	45721	118533	204216	318940	254671	251944	157829	-	-	reverse ¹
3800	125	3.3	78635	421591	789544	950381	1139840	1207856	1493567	1665340	1366849	reverse hst hvis
3800	114	3	94591	493748	826494	1459530	1376945	1513762	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	100	2.6	91732	450587	805299	1209547	1339706	1455073	1880154	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	57	1.5	20695	37280	35908	38152	40915	40324	-	-	-	reverse ²
3800	0	0	217	74	70	71	55	-	-	-	-	direct
MPAA-20 : CrI (26°C) Produced water of the “Karazhanbasunai” field (mineralization 300000-400 000 ppm)												
3800	380	10	5159	1092	234	16	5	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	190	5	8590	2719	873	365	18	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	150	3.9	75689	213632	439715	426019	297946	196830	150377	86513	73166	reverse ¹
3800	125	3.3	81763	609616	1389577	1663304	1489271	1864865	~2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	1746933	reverse hst hvis
3800	114	3	104297	685418	1516951	~2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	100	2.6	101934	659275	1509342	1938516	1839047	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	>2·10 ⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	57	1.5	23795	44196	40613	49598	47615	48826	-	-	-	reverse ²
3800	0	0	285	88	83	76	60	43	-	-	-	direct
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
MPAA-10 : CrI (80°C) Produced water of the “Zhetysai” field (mineralization 161000 ppm)												
3800	380	10	1451	518	95	8	-	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	190	5	6740	2095	484	188	29	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	150	3.9	15862	48168	180890	351895	294961	249563	193658	157409	90277	reverse ¹
3800	125	3.3	23791	81670	350837	654781	693432	905342	1143757	1059543	981160	reverse hst hvis
3800	114	3	27947	84253	379246	921642	832804	1185915	1486930	1637533	1292694	reverse hst hvis
3800	100	2.6	26189	84042	380198	809325	820813	1106439	1442934	1378620	1286493	reverse hst hvis
3800	57	1.5	9432	17639	15943	16509	17384	17839	-	-	-	reverse ²
3800	0	0	198	81	75	68	54	36	-	-	-	direct
MPAA-10 : CrI (68°C) Produced water of the “Uzen” field (mineralization 96000 ppm)												
3800	380	10	1851	739	104	14	7	-	-	-	-	destruction
3800	190	5	7084	2950	577	296	41	12	-	-	-	destruction
3800	150	3.9	24275	58169	248920	448396	401583	299361	219846	178503	118544	reverse ¹
3800	125	3.3	26794	92730	497835	741923	901478	1104393	1286802	1297354	1196820	reverse hst hvis
3800	114	3	35385	98608	539281	992430	1172797	1349636	~2·10⁶	1846348	1507917	reverse hst hvis
3800	100	2.6	32209	96970	545113	875743	1098464	1157201	1740582	1675945	1384208	reverse hst hvis
3800	57	1.5	14892	20381	18957	22497	23674	23079	-	-	-	reverse ²
3800	0	0	227	92	77	70	58	35	-	-	-	direct
Some experiments with MPAA-20 : CrI (35°C) Produced water of the “Northern Buzachi” field (mineralization 70000 ppm)												
4200	126	3	789846	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis							
5000	150	3	1299446	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis							
Some experiments with MPAA-20 distilled water (mineralization ~0 ppm) (35°C)												
2000	60	3	485340	1451282	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis						
3800	114	3	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis								
5000	150	3	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis								
Some experiments with MPAA-20 water of the Caspian Sea (mineralization ~12 900 ppm) (35°C)												
2500	75	3	310809	801843	1295376	1539680	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis
3800	114	3	1409370	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis							
5000	150	3	>2·10⁶	reverse hst hvis								

Explanation of some abbreviations according to table 2: P : CrI = polymer (P) : crosslinker (CrI); hst - high stability; hvis - high viscosity; reverse¹ - values of the viscosity of reverse suspensions at CrI = 3.9, there is an excess of the crosslinker,

which acts as a partial destructor of the corresponding gel, resulting in a sharp decrease in viscosity for all options; reverse² - viscosity values of reverse suspensions at $C_{rl} = 1.5$, there are options with insufficient amounts of crosslinker by about 2 times compared to equivalent options, resulting in a sharp decrease in viscosity for all options; MPAA-20 modified polyacrylamide with a degree of hydrolysis of approximately 20%, heat resistance of the corresponding gel up to 80°C; MPAA-10 modified polyacrylamide with a degree of hydrolysis of about 10%, heat resistance of the corresponding gel up to 80-100°C; PAA-20 polyacrylamide with a degree of hydrolysis of approximately 20%, heat resistance of the corresponding gel up to 80°C; PAA-10 polyacrylamide with a degree of hydrolysis of about 10%, heat resistance of the corresponding gel up to 80-100°C; 1 ppm = 1 mg / l = 1 mg / dm³.

Thus, based on the individual points of scientific novelty of the considered project of discovery, possible priority areas of scientific importance have been identified: the use of tertiary methods for extracting residual oils from oil-bearing formations at the late stages of field development; nanophysics; applied nanocolloidal chemistry; physical chemistry; microbiology; engineering chemistry; engineering physics, etc.

Area of practical importance of scientific discovery: oilfield nanochemistry and nanophysics for enhanced oil recovery. In accordance with the conditions of the presence of medium-large channels, low efficiency of water injection, great difficulty with clogging of channels in the injection wells of the Northern Buzachi field, a study and implementation of an injectivity profile alignment technology (IPA) based on a gel-polymer composition with delayed gelation and particles with preliminary stitching. The injection of working solutions was carried out in stages, which made it possible to effectively plug medium-large channels and obtain a positive processing result. In 2018, this technology based on this discovery was applied at the 4 injection wells, and all of them showed positive results, resulting in a net additional cumulative total oil production of 6135 tons. The actual economic efficiency due to additional oil

production is 2.24 million US dollars. Thus, the project of scientific discovery proposed by us under the name "Property of long-term self-protection of hydrogels from destructive processes of equivalently cross-linked hydrophilic polymers capable of creating a reverse nanosuspension" has found its practical confirmation in the field of oilfield nanotechnology based on nanocolloid chemistry and nanophysics. The successful application of this nanotechnology has provided a new technical solution aimed at stabilizing oil production and increasing the efficiency of operating oil fields at a late stage of development. Positive results of the implementation allow expanding the application of this scientific discovery to the Northern Buzachi field, to other fields of the Buzachi Peninsula, as well as to other regions of the Republic of Kazakhstan. This discovery is also of interest in medicine and cosmetics for the manufacture of ointment preparations based on reverse nanosuspensions.

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